

ACRIDINE DERIVATIVES. PART VI.

By S. J. DAS-GUPTA.

Certain sulphanilamido-acridines and acridyl aminobenzenesulphonamide derivatives have been prepared.

In continuation of a previous work (Das-Gupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939 16, 364) where sulphonamidophenylsulphonamidoacridine derivatives have been described, an investigation has now been undertaken to prepare certain simpler acridine derivatives of *p*-aminobenzenesulphonamide where the amide as well as the amino hydrogen of the above compound has been replaced by the acridine nucleus. The interest lies in the fact that such a replacement may increase the therapeutic activity of sulphanilamide (*cf.* Schnitzer and Silberstein, *Z. Hyg. Infek.*, 1929, 109, 519). In the present paper compounds of the types (I), (II) and (III) have been described.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Hydrochloride of 2-Chloro-4-aminobenzoic Acid.—2-Chloro-4-nitrobenzoic acid (Albert and Linnell, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1936, 55, 54T) was prepared by a modified method in almost theoretical yield. 2-Chloro-4-nitrotoluene (1 g.) was heated in a sealed tube with 5 c.c. of nitric acid (*d* 1.4) at 140-150° for several hours. On cooling the acid was obtained as colourless needles, m.p. 140-41°.

2-Chloro-4-nitrobenzoic acid (1.5 g.) was added gradually to a solution of stannous chloride (15 g.) in fuming hydrochloric acid (15 c.c.), heated on a water-bath. After the addition, heating was continued for further 2 hours. On cooling, the double salt was obtained in a crystalline form. A second crop was obtained on evaporating the mother liquor. After decomposition of the double salt (4 g.) in hot aqueous solution with sulphuretted hydrogen, the evaporation of the filtrate gave the hydrochloride of 2-chloro-4-aminobenzoic acid. Recrystallised from water in colourless needles it had m.p. 187°. (Found: Cl, 33.92. $C_7H_6O_2NCl$, HCl requires Cl, 34.13 per cent).

Hydrochloride of 2-Chloro-5-aminobenzoic Acid.—2-Chloro-5-nitrobenzoic acid (m.p. 159-61°) was prepared from 2-chloro-5-nitrotoluene in almost theoretical yield by a similar method and was reduced as above. The hydrochloride of 2-chloro-5-aminobenzoic acid was crystallised from water in colourless prismatic needles, m.p. 257°. (Found: Cl, 33.98. $C_7H_6O_2NCl$, HCl requires Cl, 34.13 per cent).

2-Chloro-4-(p-acetylaminobenzene) sulphonamidobenzoic Acid.—Hydrochloride of 2-chloro-4-aminobenzoic acid (1 g.) was treated with sodium carbonate (0.5 g) and a little water and then *p*-acetylaminobenzenesulphonyl chloride (1 g.) was added and the mixture rubbed in a mortar for about 2 hours. Sodium carbonate was added occasionally to keep the mixture alkaline. The mixture was left overnight and after dilution with water filtered. The filtrate on acidification with hydrochloric acid gave the acid (0.6 g.) as colourless needles from dilute alcohol, m.p. 142°. (Found: N, 7.35. $C_{15}H_{13}O_5N_2ClS$ requires N, 7.60 per cent).

2-Chloro-5-(p-acetylaminobenzene) sulphonamidobenzoic acid was prepared from the hydrochloride of 5-amino-2-chlorobenzoic acid and *p*-acetylaminobenzenesulphonyl chloride exactly in the same way as described above. The acid was crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless microscopic crystals, m.p. 263°. (Found: N, 7.48. $C_{15}H_{13}O_5N_2ClS$ requires N, 7.60 per cent).

4-(p-Acetylaminobenzene) sulphonamido-4'-methoxydiphenylamine 2-carboxylic Acid.—4-(*p*-Acetylaminobenzene) sulphonamido-2-chlorobenzoic acid (1 mol.), *p*-anisidine (1 mol.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (1 mol.) were refluxed together in amyl alcoholic solution with little copper powder for several hours. The mixture after dilution with water was distilled in steam to remove amyl alcohol. On filtration of the residual liquid and acidification with hydrochloric acid in cold, the diphenylamine was precipitated and was crystallised from dilute alcohol (charcoal) in almost colourless microscopic needles, m.p. 158-60°. It gave the usual

test of diphenylamine. (Found: N, 8.97. $C_{22}H_{21}O_6N_3S$ requires N, 9.23 per cent).

5 - (*p*-Acetylaminobenzene)sulphonamido-4-methoxydiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid was prepared from 5-(*p*-acetylaminobenzene)sulphonamido-2-chlorobenzoic acid and *p*-anisidine in the same way as in the previous case, in almost colourless needles from dilute alcohol (charcoal), m.p. 218-20°. (Found: N, 9.1. $C_{22}H_{21}O_6N_3S$ requires N, 9.23 per cent).

2 - (4'-Acetylaminobenzene)sulphonamido-7-methoxy-5-chloroacridine (structure analogous to I).—The 4-(*p*-acetylaminobenzene)sulphonamido-4-methoxydiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid was refluxed with excess of phosphorus oxychloride on a water-bath for more than one hour. Excess of oxychloride was removed in vacuum. The residual mass was treated with ice-cold water and made just alkaline with ammonia. The chloroacridine was collected, washed with water and crystallised from a mixture of acetone and water (1 : 2) in reddish microscopic crystals, m.p. 245-47° (decomp.). It gives fluorescence in dilute solutions in acetone, alcohol and benzene, and is soluble in both acids and alkalis. (Found: N, 9.24; Cl, 7.61. $C_{22}H_{18}O_4N_3ClS$ requires N, 9.22; Cl, 7.79 per cent).

3 - (4'-Acetylaminobenzene)sulphonamido-7-methoxy-5-chloroacridine (structure analogous to II) was prepared from 5-(*p*-acetylaminobenzene)sulphonamido-4'-methoxydiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid in the same manner as described above and crystallised from a mixture of acetone and water in orange microscopic crystals, m.p. 243-44° (decomp.). It gives fluorescence in dilute solutions in alcohol, acetone and benzene. (Found: N, 8.89. $C_{22}H_{18}O_4N_3ClS$ requires N, 9.22 per cent).

3 - (4'-Aminobenzene)sulphonamido-7-methoxy-5-chloroacridine.—3-(*p*-Acetylaminobenzene)sulphonamido-7-methoxy-5-chloroacridine (0.5 g.) was hydrolysed by heating with 12 c.c. of aqueous alcoholic hydrochloric acid (5%) for 20 minutes when a clear solution was obtained. After cooling and diluting with little water, the solution was neutralised with ammonia when a solid separated. It was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from dilute alcohol in reddish needles, melting indefinitely at ca 180°. It gives fluorescence in dilute solutions and also responds to diazo reactions. (Found: N, 10.39; Cl, 8.37. $C_{20}H_{14}O_3N_3ClS$ requires N, 10.16; Cl, 8.58 per cent).

N⁴-(2-Chloro-7-methoxy)-acridylaminobenzenesulphonamide (structure analogous to II).—Equimolecular quantities of 7-methoxy-2:5-dichloroacridine and *p*-aminobenzenesulphonamide were heated in phenol at 110-120° for 2 hours. After cooling the mixture was poured into dilute sodium hydroxide solution, filtered and washed. The solid collected was crystallised from a large volume of alcohol in small yellow needles, m.p. 286°. (Found: N, 9.9. $C_{20}H_{14}O_3N_3ClS$ requires N, 10.16 per cent). The com-

pound is slightly soluble in acids but insoluble in alkalis. It gives fluorescence in dilute alcoholic solutions.

*N*⁴-(2-Chloro-7-methoxy)acridylaminobenzenesulphondiethylamide.—Equimolecular quantities of 7-methoxy-2:5-dichloroacridine and *p*-aminobenzenesulphondiethylamide were heated in phenol at about 120° for 2 hours. The mixture was poured into dilute sodium hydroxide solution when a semi-solid mass separated, which was washed with cold water and crystallised from ether in orange-yellow needles, m.p. 175°. (Found: N, 8.67. C₂₄H₂₄O₂N₂ClS requires N, 8.94 per cent). By passing dry hydrogen chloride through an ethereal solution of this compound the hydrochloride separated which was crystallised from alcohol-ether mixture in small deep orange needles, m.p. 260-61°. The base as well as the hydrochloride give fluorescence in dilute alcoholic solutions.

*N*⁴-(7-Methoxy)-acridylaminobenzenesulphondiethylamide.—Equimolecular quantities of 7-methoxy-5-chloroacridine and *p*-aminobenzenesulphondiethylamide were heated in phenol at 120-130° for 2 hours. After pouring the mixture into cold dilute sodium hydroxide solution, a semi-solid mass separated, which after treatment with ether solidified. It was obtained as yellow microscopic crystals from alcohol and water (1:1), m.p. 263-64°. It is insoluble in alkalis but soluble in acids and gives fluorescence in dilute alcoholic solutions. (Found: N, 9.28. C₂₃H₂₂O₂N₂ClS requires N, 9.55 per cent).

*N*⁴-(2-Chloro-7-methoxy)-acridylaminobenzenesulphonacetamide.—Equimolecular quantities of 7-methoxy-2:5-dichloroacridine and *p*-aminobenzenesulphonacetamide (m.p. 182°) were heated in phenol at 150-160° for 3 hours. After pouring into ice-cold dilute sodium hydroxide solution a semi-solid mass was obtained. This was washed with water and then treated with ether when a solid was obtained. Orange microscopic crystals separated from a large volume of alcohol and water (1:1), m.p. 248-50°. It is soluble in dilute acids and alkalis. (Found: N, 8.95. C₂₂H₁₈O₄N₂ClS requires N, 9.22 per cent).

*N*⁴-(7-Methoxy)-acridylaminobenzenesulphonacetamide was prepared from 7-methoxy-5-chloroacridine and *p*-aminobenzenesulphonacetamide in the same manner as in the previous case. Orange microscopic crystals were obtained from alcohol and water (1:1), m.p. 143-45°. The compound is soluble in water, more in alkalis and acids. (Found: N, 9.51. C₂₁H₁₆O₃N₂ClS requires N, 9.87 per cent).

The author wishes to express his sincere thanks to Dr. U. P. Basu for his kind interest in this investigation.